

THE NEW NATURE WITH THE PRINCIPLE OF THE INFINITE PART OF MATTER AND THE NEW APPLIED MATHEMATICS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14779539>

Published Date: 31-January-2025

Abstract: An assumption of the existence of impersonal zero is made and the inductive methodology is followed, which leads to the transition of male zero face and autobirth at the same time female zero. The female zero in his imagination captures the infinite points. It oscillates the volume of the ether and successively forms a control center, from which the universes that follow originate.

Differential calculus, applied mathematics, depends on the principle of indivisibility of matter and infinitely divisible. Here we adopted the principle of infinitely divisible and in marginal cases the interpolation of discrete mathematics with the principle of indivisibility of matter is necessary. This is because, within the matter that will exist on the principle of infinitely divisible, there will be discrete bodies, hence the necessity of both mathematics in parallel.

We have published the discrete mathematics applicable to existing matter, on the principle of indivisibility. I asked the center of control, with an etheric program, to adopt the principle of the infinite part, and I hope that it will adopt it and that the new nature will apply.

We adopt the $dx = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x = 0$, where x tends to zero, and when $y = kx$, $dy = kdx$, i.e. we avoid $dy = k(x+dx) - kx$, which the inline calculus uses, because it gives incorrect results. When $y = kx^2$, we calculate $dy = kx dx$, while the established mathematics, $dy = 2kdx + dx^2$.

Definitions of kinematic physics equations are given and it is easily understood that they are correct, while the inconsistent equations given by physics come from the use of $dy = k(x+dx) - kx$.

Mathematics, calculus or differential calculus, which are consistent, are developed. The product and quotient of two functions, etc. are different.

Keywords: inductive methodology, control center, both mathematics in parallel.

1. INTRODUCTION

The universes functioned and were structured on the principle of the least indivisible particle, matter,¹ and applied mathematics was those of discrete magnitudes, which had no boundary constantly tending towards zero.

After the conversation I had with a friend, I created a program-mandate to the center of the universes, to adopt and apply the principle of the infinite part of the particle of matter and the limit to zero. Then new applied mathematics is needed, because differential calculus adopted wrong choices². And correct his mistakes.

¹ THE TOTAL THEORY, international journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research volume 8 issue 2 April 2020-September 2020

² "ALEKOS CHARALAMPOPOULOS, OVERTURNING OF INFINITESIMAL CALCULUS AND RESTORATION OF THE MATHEMATICS IN CONNECTION WITH THE COSMIC THEORY "THE IDION" International Journal of Mathematics and Physical Sciences Research, Oct2020-Mar2021" and in the same "THE FINAL FORM OF THE ATOMIC THEORY, Oct2023-Mar2024".

2. METHODOLOGY

Like the ancient Greek philosophers, they set the principles to make their theory, and here we set principles. I would say philosophical the principle of the preexistence of zero, but mathematical and physical the principle of the infinite part of matter.

Democritus set as a principle the minimum indivisibility of matter, atom, and Anaxagoras set as a principle the infinitely divisible of matter. Democritus combines the discrete mathematics we have already published, and Anaxagoras matches the calculus, with the limit to zero, in mathematics here.

We use definitions that are reasonable, accepted as reasonable, and the definition emerges as a prerequisite, as a principle.

Induction, philosophical induction and mathematical induction are widely used and are, along with abduction, the backbone of this work.

Finally, the description of creation is used, which uses induction and abduction as tools.

A LITTLE ABOUT THE EXISTENCE OF THE IMMATERIAL

By applying the methodology, we set the first principle. The premise of the existence of zero, that is, that it has always existed outside time and space, had no dimensions, was immaterial. It was something non-personal and therefore genderless, it was a higher ultimate reality.

As physicist Lundvich Buhner³, a materialist friend of Marx, points out, force is immaterial and exists next to matter. The immaterial force, when it affects matter, creates kinetic energy. The force is $F=mdx/dt^2$ (we use the symbols of differential calculus) and $\int Fdx = \int m \frac{dx}{dt^2} dx = mx \frac{dx}{dt^2} = mxa = m \frac{x^2}{t^2} = mv^2$ (see integrals below), kinetic energy. This is magnitude, it is invested in mass matter m , and it is something immaterial, it has no dimensions of space.

From the interaction of two masses that have gravity, but also from the interaction of two electric charges, a force and potential energy arise. For almost stationary bodies, the force is $F=k/r^2$ and the potential energy $F=k/r$, and for rotating bodies, $F=k'/r^3$ and the potential energy $F=k'/r^2$. Forces and dynamic energies, and all energies in general, are immaterial quantities.

Thermal and magnetic energy are also immaterial.

The energies, infinite nest in the reservoir of impersonal zero and supply the particles of matter, when necessary, with the appropriate energy.

The forces that generate potential energy, at some point when the beginning of time took place, competed with the potential that cause kinetic energy, and impersonal zero, part of it, falls into zero personal. And as a staff, it's male. And at the same time, the female personal zero is born itself.

Persons invent ideas-concepts, make thoughts, stress plans, make theories and the highest theory.

Grafted with the thoughts of the male, female zero gives birth! It creates it.

In his mind, he captures distribution of infinite points, in infinite space. The points are dimensionless, they do not extend in space each, the distribution of points extends to the imaginary space of the female zero. The impersonal zero, gives kinetic and dynamic energy to the points, from the tank of impersonal zero. The points began to oscillate, in volume oscillation and with a phase difference. From the point without dimensions and with zero volume, a wave begins, ether develops, matter ether. A volume of ether alternates with zero and negative and again zero and then positive ether volume. And with the phase difference of the pulsating points, the complementary continuous, elastic, with a small viscosity (less than air), ether is created.

The female zero identifies denser points that oscillate from infinite space to the center. In the center is created a huge bubble of the dilute original ether, the transcendental non-substance, with around it a denser ether, the enosia. The bubble has a crust, the densest ether, the same.

³ POWER AND MATTER

The pressure of infinite ether (enosia) in the bubble is infinite, it has the properties of solid (elasticity infinite), the properties of liquid (viscosity small) and the properties of gas (denser near the bubble, thinner outwards and then constant density). The propagation of a perturbation in the ether is instantaneously transmitted throughout its space, the infinite, the empirically infinite.

Due to the high pressures, part of the dense crust of the bubble "evaporates", creating infinitesimally small grains of dense ether, moving with the energy of impersonal zero, like the ideal gas. The grains collide with each other, many fall vertically and with momentum into the crust, make a small dent that closes behind it. And it is a very small bubble, electrically charged and the ancestor of the particles of atoms (two bubbles make up the hydrogen atom). Due to far they will move away, gather in space, form gases, the origin of star births.

The bubbles that are created, created on the principle of indivisibility of matter, are indivisible. And applied mathematics is discrete and there is no limit tending to zero.

I have already instructed the control center of the universes, in the central bubble, to adopt the principle of infinite divisible and boundary to zero. Here, too, applied mathematics is of differential calculus, but the one we will develop, if the instruction prevails. That is, now there will be death and bubbles, in smaller and smaller there will be those, from the largest, when they die.

INTRODUCTION TO THE MATHEMATICS OF THE INFINITELY INDIVISIBLE

From the theory of probability and combinations, we know that, $0!=1$. Then

$$\frac{0!}{0!} = 1 = \frac{5!}{5!} = \frac{5}{5} = \frac{4}{4} = \frac{3}{3} = \frac{2}{2} = \frac{1}{1} = \frac{0!}{0!} = \frac{0}{0} = \frac{\infty!}{\infty!} = \frac{\infty}{\infty} = 1$$

So $0/0$ =undefined, but sometimes depending on the problem, $0/0=1$. And $0=c$. Also, $\frac{\infty}{\infty} = \frac{c}{c} = 1$. That is, infinity is constant.

According to the ancient Greek language, infinity is a compound word (it consists of the deprivative α and with experience or with the not experiance). So, the concept of infinity in ancient Greece is what does not fall under experience, but also what has no end.

So, the atoms of our universe are infinite, empirically infinite, and the space of the ether without an empirical end (for man).

THE APPLIED DIFFERENTIAL CALCULUS, IN AN INFINITE PART

When universes have the infinite divisible, there is a limit that constantly tends towards zero.

$$y = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad dx = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x = 0$$

dx is the infinitesimal variation, if $x=t$, then is instantaneous time. The definitions that are the first equations are the next ones and you judge if they are correct.

$$\begin{aligned} y=kx, & & dy=kdx & & dy/dx=k \\ y=kx^2 & & dy=kdx^2 & & dy/dx^2=k \\ dy/dx=kdx=k(dx/dy)dy & \text{and} & d^2y/dx^2=kdy, & \text{also,} & \\ y=kx^2 & & dy=kxdx & & dy/dx=kx \end{aligned}$$

The distance S , $S=S_0+VT$ $DS=VDT$ $DS/DT=V$

$$s=s_0+v_0t+at^2 \quad ds=v_0dt+adt^2 \quad ds/dt^2=a \quad ds/dt=v_0+adt,$$

and, $v \frac{ds}{dt} = v_0 + \frac{ds}{dt^2} dt = v_0 + v_c$ and v_c are specific, the limit is specific.

The velocity is v , when the body has acceleration a .

$$v=v_0+at \quad dv=adt \quad dv/dt=a$$

The differential calculus that already exists, gives a different definition of the limit, gives,

$$y = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \{(x + dx) - x\} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} dx = 0$$

The derivative is a limit,

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\{(x+dx)-x\}}{dx}$$

So, in the equations above, just like we found. $\frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\{k(x+dx)-kx\}}{dx} = k$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\{(kx+kdx)^2-(kx)^2\}}{dx} = \frac{2kxdx+kdx^2}{dx} = 2kx + kdx = 2kx$$

Here we see that the standard differential calculus provides a solution so that the limit dy/dx is proportional to the variable of twice x , so incorrect.

Precisely because the standard differential calculus uses this limit, it gives,

$$s = v_0t + \frac{1}{2}at^2$$

That is, it puts the 1/2 that we do not have in the equation and which we give by definition and is reasonable. Judge our definition if it is plausible and this above equation if it is correct, because the equation of the standard differential calculus, when $a=g$ the acceleration of gravity, gives $g=9.81 \text{ m/sec}^2$, instead of the correct $g=4.9$.

It will be,

$$\frac{ds}{dt} = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{\{v_0(t+dt) + \frac{1}{2}a(t+dt)^2 - v_0t - \frac{1}{2}at^2\}}{dt} = \frac{v_0dt + atdt + \frac{1}{2}adt^2}{dt} = v_0 + at + \frac{1}{2}adt = v_0 + at$$

That is, the velocity of the body will be, which velocity is proportional to the variable of time t , is not a limit to instantaneous time, but continuous. The limit usually tends to a specific value rather than a continuous variable. Therefore, we must reject the limit of the standard differential calculus, because we gave the plausible definition of the equation, which does not have 1/2. $s = v_0t + at^2$

INVERSE FUNCTIONS

A function $f(x)$ is an inverse of a function $g(x)$, when, $f(g(x))=x$ and $g(f(x))=x$. In this case, $g=f^{-1}$, $f=g^{-1}$.

The function $f(x)=\log_a x$, is an inverse of the function, $g(x)=a^x$, by default, i.e. we defined this. And so, $f(x)=y=\ln x$, is an inverse of $g(x)=y'=e^x$.

That is, it is, $g(f(x)) = f(g(x)) = x = e^{\ln x} = \ln e^x$

According to the limit we adopted for the new differential calculus, it will be $dy=\ln dx$. But the,

$$dx = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x = 0$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{\ln dx}{dx} = \frac{\ln dx}{\frac{dx}{\frac{dy}{dy}}} \rightarrow \frac{dy}{dx} \frac{dx}{dy} = \frac{\ln dx}{dy} = 1$$

And, $g(x)=y'=e^x$, so,

$$\frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} = \frac{\frac{dx}{e^{\frac{dx}{dy}}}}{dx} = \frac{\frac{dx}{\ln e^{\frac{dx}{dy}}}}{dx} = \frac{\frac{dx}{dy}}{dy} = \frac{dx}{dy}$$

So, and $\frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} = \frac{\ln dx}{\ln e^{dx}} = \frac{dx}{e^{dx}} \quad \text{καλ} \quad \frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} = \frac{dx}{dy}$

Thus, the slopes of the two inverse functions are equal and inverse.

The derivative, because dx is a limit that tends, but does not reach zero, will be,

$$\frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} = \frac{\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} e^x}{\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x}$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{\ln dx}{dx} = \frac{\ln dx}{\ln e^{dx}} = \frac{dx}{e^{dx}} = \frac{\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x}{\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} e^x}$$

$dy/dx=1/ dy'/dx$ (they are inverse in the sense we know).

Then, and $\frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} = \infty$ $\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{\ln dx}{dx} = \frac{dx}{e^{dx}} = 0$

That is, zero and infinity are inverse derivatives of y, and y', is $0=1/\infty$.

We give the graph of $y' = e^x = \exp(x)$,

The derivative dy'/dx , is the slope of y' . And the slope of y' is infinite, (parallel to the y-axis of the figure, where $dx=0$), when x becomes infinity. That is, the limit, $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} x = 0$

because it's a limit.
$$\frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} = \frac{1}{0} = \infty$$

When it comes to the limit, then we handle discrete mathematics, and,

$$\frac{\Delta y'}{\Delta x} = \frac{e^{\Delta x}}{\Delta x} = \frac{e^M}{M}$$

M is approaching zero from both positive and negative numbers to the limit. But only when x is tending to zero, y tends to positive infinity, and the slope of y' is that predicted, infinite. In regions of x that are less than infinity, then c also depends on M. And x is less than infinity and greater than zero. That is why we told you that dx is constantly tending but not reaching zero, and we should adopt discrete mathematics as complementary. And in problems, dx can also be Δx . And then we go to the discrete mathematics, which complements these here.

$$\frac{\Delta y'}{\Delta x} = \frac{e^{\Delta x}}{\Delta x} = \frac{e^M}{M} = c$$

THE WRONG DEFINITION OF THE FUNCTION $y = \ln x$

At this point, I would like to give you the wrong and arbitrary definition of the established differential calculus. So⁴, the definition is:

The function of the natural Neperian logarithm is,

$$\ln x = \int_1^x \frac{1}{t} dt, \quad \ln 1 = \int_1^1 \frac{1}{t} dt = 0$$

From this erroneous and arbitrary definition of the logarithm lies the derivative of e^x .

It should be, however, according to established mathematics,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln x &= \int_0^x \frac{1}{t} dt, & \ln 1 &= \int_0^1 \frac{1}{t} dt = \ln 1 - \ln 0 \\ \ln 0 &= \int_0^0 \frac{1}{t} dt = \ln 0 - \ln 0 = 0 \end{aligned}$$

⁴ CALCULUS, Finney-Weir-Giordano, p. 441

But mainstream science found $\ln 1=0$, not $\ln 0=0$.

We remind you that $y=\ln x$ is an inverse of $y'=e^x$, i.e. according to the above,

$$e^{\ln x} = \ln e^x$$

$$e^{\ln 1} = \ln e^1 = 1 = \ln e = 1$$

$$e^{\ln 0} = \ln e^0 = 0 = \ln 1 = 1$$

and $\ln 0=\ln 1=1$

(see below, $\ln 1=1$).

THE PROPERTIES OF LOGARITHMS

We will have, and, $e^{\ln a} + \ln e^b = a + b$, $\ln(a + b) = \ln(e^{\ln a} + \ln e^b) = \ln a + \ln b$

$$e^{\ln a} - \ln e^b = a - b, \quad \ln(a - b) = \ln(e^{\ln a} - \ln e^b) = \ln a - \ln b$$

Also

$$\text{and then, } e^{\ln a} \ln e^b = ab$$

$$\ln(ab) = \ln(e^{\ln a} \ln e^b) = \{\ln(e^{\ln a})\}\{\ln(\ln e^b)\} = \ln a \cdot \ln b$$

Which is different from the standard differential calculus (there it is addition, not multiplication, of logarithms).

A corollary of this property is, $\ln(a \cdot 1)=\ln a=\ln a \cdot \ln 1$ and $\ln 1=1$ (we promised it to you above), then,

$$e^{\ln 1} = 1 = \ln e^1 = \ln e = 1$$

This is very important. $1=\ln e$, is a unit.

Let's go to the quotient now,

$$\text{we will have, } \frac{\ln e^a}{e^{\ln b}} = \frac{a}{b}$$

$$\ln\left(\frac{a}{b}\right) = \ln\left(\frac{\ln e^a}{e^{\ln b}}\right) = \left(\frac{\ln(\ln e^a)}{\ln(e^{\ln b})}\right) = \frac{\ln a}{\ln b}$$

That is, the logarithm quotient is equal to the quotient of the logarithms of the quantities that make up the quotient and not their difference, given by the established differential calculus.

And finally, the logarithm of power is, $\ln a^x = \ln e^{kx} = kx$, $a=e^k$. That is, it is not $\ln a^x = x \ln a$, as the standard differential calculus accepts.

Now let's look at the derivative of $F=k/R^c$, which will concern us in the future,

$$\frac{dF}{dR} = \lim_{R \rightarrow 0} \frac{k}{R^c} = \infty$$

The slope dF/dR , is perpendicular to the axis R and parallel to the y -axis, tangent to the function, at large R , i.e. when $R \rightarrow \infty$. When it comes to discrete mathematics, $\Delta F/\Delta R=k/(\Delta R)$, then the slope is on the curve of the figure.

TRIGONOMETRIC PRODUCERS

When $R=R_{\max}\sin(\omega t+\pi/2)=R_{\max}\cos(\omega t)$, $dR=R_{\max}\sin(\omega t)$.

In the figure, the spring oscillates on the x-axis, but the maximum radius is reached on the y-axis, at point A. In the center, the maximum speed $dR/dt=v_{\max}$ is achieved, but also the maximum acceleration,

$$\frac{dR}{dt} = v = \frac{R_{\max}}{dt} \sin(\omega dt) = \frac{2\pi R_{\max}}{2\pi dt} \sin(\omega dt) = \frac{v_{\max} T}{2\pi} \left(\frac{\sin(\omega dt)}{\frac{\omega dt}{\omega}} \right) = \frac{v_{\max} T}{2\pi} \frac{\sin(\omega dt)}{\omega dt} = v_{\max} \frac{\sin(\omega dt)}{\omega dt} = v_{\max}$$

Speed is limit, this is the speed of circular rotation. On the x-axis of the figure, the velocity fluctuates, such as, $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{R}{t} = v = \frac{dR}{dt} = v_{\max} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sin(\omega dt)}{\omega dt} = v_{\max}$

Because, $R=R_{\max}\cos(\omega t)$, $dR/dt=(R_{\max}/dt)\cos(\omega t)$, we have,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{R}{t} = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \tilde{v} = \frac{dR}{dt} = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \frac{R_{\max}}{t} \cos(\omega t) \right\} = v_{\max} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \{ \cos(\omega t) \}$$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\frac{R}{t}}{\cos(\omega t)} \right) = v_{\max} = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} v_{\max}$$

$$\frac{R}{t} = \tilde{v} = v_{\max} \cos(\omega t)$$

And the second derivative, but again this is a limit, it happens on the periphery of circular motion, so, $\frac{dR}{dt^2} = a =$

$$\frac{v_{\max}}{dt} \sin(\omega dt) = \frac{v_{\max} T}{T} \frac{\omega \sin(\omega dt)}{\omega dt} = 2\pi a_{\max}$$

$$\tilde{a} = 2\pi a_{\max} \sin\left(\omega t + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) = 2\pi a_{\max} \cos(\omega t)$$

$R=R_{\max}\sin(\omega t+\varphi)$ when $\varphi=\pi/2$, and $t=0,2\pi,4\pi,\dots$, then $R=R_{\max}$, of simple harmonic oscillation. But, $\cos(0)-\cos(10)=0.01519$, $\cos(90)-\cos(80)=0.1736$. So, has a greater velocity difference Δv near zero, from where the spring oscillation starts, $dv = v_{\max} \cos(\omega dt)$, $v_{\max} \{ \cos(90)-\cos(80) \} = v_{\max} 0.1736$. While $\cos(0)-\cos(10)=0.01519$ near the unfolding of the radius and when the acceleration will be zero (immobilizes the spring-bound body when it acquires a maximum displacement $\pi/2$ ($\cos(\pi/2)=0$)). That is, it has at 0 degrees a maximum radius on the y-axis and has maximum acceleration and velocity, on the x-axis, where the spring oscillates on axis x. Thus, the maximum velocity is achieved at the center of the oscillation at zero angle, as is the acceleration $\Delta v/\Delta t$ (in both cases, velocity and acceleration are proportional to $\cos(\omega t)=\cos(0)=1$, $\omega t=0,2\pi,4\pi,\dots$).

PRODUCT DERIVATIVES AND DIVISION OF FUNCTIONS

When $z(x)=f(x)g(x)$, then, $\frac{dz(x)}{dx} = f(x) \frac{dg(x)}{dx} = g(x) \frac{df(x)}{dx} = \frac{df(x)}{dx} \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} = \frac{df(x)}{dx} \frac{f(x)}{g(x)}$

When $z(x)=f(x)/g(x)$, then, $\frac{dz(x)}{dx} = \frac{df(x)}{g(x)} = \frac{df(x)}{dx} \frac{1}{g(x)} = \frac{df(x)}{dx} \frac{f(x)}{z(x)} = \frac{df(x)}{dx} \frac{f(x)}{z(x)}$

$$\frac{dz(x)}{dx} = \frac{1}{g(x)} \frac{df(x)}{dx} = \frac{z(x)}{f(x)} \frac{df(x)}{dx}$$

$$\frac{\frac{dz(x)}{dx}}{\frac{dg(x)}{dx}} = \frac{z(x)}{g(x)}$$

And, $z(x)=f(x)/g(x)$, then, $\frac{dz(x)}{dx} = f(x) \frac{d(1)}{g(x)} = f(x) \frac{d(x^0)}{g(x)} = f(x) \frac{x^{-1}}{g(x)} = \frac{f(x)}{xg(x)} = \frac{z(x)}{x}$

Stable derivative, $y=c$, $\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{d(c.1)}{dx} = \frac{d(cx^0)}{dx} = c \frac{d(x^0)}{dx} = cx^{-1} = \frac{c}{x}$

INTEGRALS

We will have,

$$y=k \quad y' = \int k dx = kx$$

$$y=kx \quad y' = \int kx dx = kx^2$$

$$y=kx^2 \quad y' = \int kx^2 dx = kx^3$$

$$s=s_0+at^2 \quad s' = \int (s_0 + at^2) dt = s_0t + at^3$$

$$v=v_0+at \quad v' = \int (v_0 + at) dt = v_0t + at^2$$

$$\frac{dy'}{dx} = \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} \quad y' = \int \frac{dy'}{dx} dx = dy' = \int \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} dx = \int e^{dx} = e^x$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx} = \frac{dx}{e^{dx}} = \frac{\ln dx}{dx} \quad y' = \int \frac{\ln dx}{dx} dx = \int \ln dx = \ln x$$

$$y(x)=f(x)g(x) \quad y' = g(x) \int f(x) dx = f(x) \int g(x) dx$$

$$y(x)=f(x)/g(x) \quad y' = \frac{1}{g(x)} \int f(x) dx = f(x) \int \frac{1}{g(x)} dx = \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \int x^0 dx = x \frac{f(x)}{g(x)}$$

$$y(x)=c \quad y' = \int \frac{cx^0}{dx} dx = c \int \frac{x^0}{dx} dx = cx$$

$$y(x)=1/x \quad y' = \int \frac{x^{-1}}{dx} dx = x^0 = 1$$

$$y' = z = e^{dx}, \quad \int z dx = zx = xe^{dx}, \quad \int xz dx = \int x \frac{e^{dx}}{dx} dx = zx^2 = \int xe^{dx} dx$$

$$, \quad zx^2 = \int xe^{dx} dx = x \int e^{dx} = xe^x = x^2 e^{dx} e^x = xe^{dx}$$

$$dy' = z = e^{dx} = \frac{1}{x^2} \int xe^{dx} dx$$

.But $\int dy' = \int e^{dx} = y' = e^x$

And for the logarithm, $y=\ln x$, $dy=\ln dx$, $dy'/dx=dx/dy$, so,

$$y(x) = \int \frac{dy(x)}{dx} dx = \int (\ln dx) = \ln x$$

EPILOGUE

An assumption of the existence of impersonal zero is made and the inductive methodology is followed, which leads to the transition of male zero face and autobirth at the same time female zero. The female zero in his imagination captures the infinite points. It oscillates the volume of the ether and successively forms a control center, from which the universes that follow originate.

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